

A Real-time framework for detection of abnormal activities in videos using CFS and BoF classifiers

¹Dr. Basavaraj G M, ²Dr. Rajashekhar B Somasagar, ³Dr. Ashok Kusagur

¹ Associate Professor, Department of ECE, Nagarjuna College of Engineering and Technology, Bengaluru, Karnataka, India

² Associate Professor Department of ECE, G M Institute of Technology, Davanagere, Karnataka, India

³ Associate Professor, Department of EEE, UBDTCE, Davanagere, Karnataka, India

¹gmb2206@gmail.com

²rajashekharbs@gmail.com

Abstract: Detecting the behavior of crowd in real life scenario is still a challenging task for researchers. In the last two decades, several methods have been reported by researchers to overcome this problem. Most of them are based on only low semantic features like gray value, motion estimation, and gradient information. These features are not sufficient to provide discriminative information of the crowded scenes. In this paper, we proposed a framework based on optical flow approach, which incorporates heat-map generation, the point of interest extraction segmentation and feature extraction. It follows Bag of Feature (BoF) classification model to catch abnormalities in crowded scenes. This frame work is applied on three scenario of UMN (University of Minnesota) dataset which outperforms other state-of-the-art methods in terms of classification accuracy. The average classification accuracy got from the experiment is 99.6%.

KEYWORDS: Motion estimation, Heat-map, optical flow, points of interest extraction, Bag of feature.

1. Introduction

Human population is increasing rapidly day by day. Hence, the crowded scenes are more common in a practical scenario. However, taking action at the right time may reduce the impact of the unwanted crowded scenarios as it may turn out to be a disaster if we don't pay attention at the beginning of the crowded scenario. Airport, railway station and shopping malls are places where safety and security of the people are most important and also challenging. From the last few decades, it has attracted lot of attention by the researchers to sort out these problems. So it is essential to know about the behavior of the crowd at the right time. Video surveillance system [1] is a practical application of such type of requirement.

Many researchers have proposed various algorithms to recognize, track and understand crowd behavior [2] in a video scene. However, they specifically focused on low semantic features. Therefore in real life complex crowded scene, their algorithms are not able to handle the scenario well. Under such conditions catching an abnormal activity is very important and a challenging task for researchers.

Wenxi Liu et al. [3] has presented an architecture based on AMM's model, to detect the crowd behavior of the captured scenario. To describe the motion of the crowd, the individual feature is considered along with the holistic feature. These holistic features are based on the proposed correlation feature. The result illustrates that it is suitable for recognizing a lower dense crowd. In [4] an algorithm is presented which works the model for low to

medium crowded scenes and implements a trajectory behavior learning process. The algorithm is suitable for tracking of the non-linear motion of each pedestrian. PETS and ARENA datasets are used to accomplish this approach. This is suitable for indoor and outdoor scenes.

In [5] a novel algorithm is proposed, which is based on an acceleration feature to detect abnormal crowd behavior. The algorithm states about the current feature and global feature of the scenes. The proposed algorithm is able to match the pixels, and can catch the speed variation easily. Based on the level of threshold, the system provides very promising results.

In [6] a behavior features is summarized, to capture the crowd of people behavior and such features are explained for encoding the behavior of the crowd, which might be global, local, spatial or temporal. Optical flow [7], foreground object size [8] histogram of (direction, texture, motion) [9] are a different type of features. In [10] a Dirichlet allocation model is proposed for a crowded scenario, where direction, position, and velocity are used. A Markova model is adopted [11] for detecting anomalous actions, where the optical flow is estimated at each frame level. This detection is computed based on the likelihood matrix. In [12] a trajectory is created for normal video as well as abnormal videos and compared for differentiating abnormal activities. A well-organized model is developed in [13], which is a combination of dynamic texture and outliers. In [14] a limited utility was generated based on a feature of magnitude, position, and direction incorporated with a Bayesian framework to avoid detection through the model.

In this paragraph discussed the problem of analyzing the behavior of high crowded scene in various scenarios. We also proposed a real-time framework on optical flow pattern followed by Bag of feature (BoF) classification model. The inner region of motion activity is taking out by the motion heat map. This reduces the processing time and provides a improved end result in terms of performance. The point of interest which is useful in the computation of optical flow pattern is extracted based on region of motion activity. Optical flow pattern produces a feature vector. BoF classification model utilizes this feature vector to build a classification model. This classification model gives improved performance compare to the state of art models.

Further, paper is organized into four sections, which are as follows. In section 2 we presented related to work in crowd activity recognition field, section 3 describes about the proposed framework applied in our work. In section 4 result is evaluated and discussed and conclusion is given in last section.

2. Related work

Related work has been distributed into two categories. Crowd density estimation comes in the first category while the abnormal activity detection is the second category. An overview of the second category of related to work is summarized here.

Robert Bensch et.al [15] has proposed a motion based approach to develop a prototype pattern to distinguish normal and abnormal activity of a video sample. The prototype is trained from multiple sequences to accept variations. Super trajectories based clustering is used for robust and efficient representation of motion.

Wei Shen et.al [16] has proposed which uses two sparse dictionaries along with saliency to detect the abnormal scene in the video. He has combined multistate histogram of oriented gradient (MHOG) and a multiscale histogram of optical flow (MHOF) into a single unit which represents the feature of spatial-temporal domain in the crowd.

YIRAN XUE et.al [17] has developed a model to detect the crowd behavior by analyzing the particles which take part in the collision. The characteristics of the individual particle are evaluated by a general trend model. After getting the characteristics, he has proposed the Boltzmann model (LBM). The collision effect is observed by analyzing the variation in crowd particle. The model predicts the abnormality through iterations of concurrent streaming and collision stages. Only few beginning frames are required to initialize the process. There is no training needed for this approach.

In the field of intelligent crowd abnormal detection, most of the methods mainly emphasis on local features which is inspired by the model found in another discipline like fluid dynamics and social dynamics to represent motion analysis. In this paper, Shuang Wu et.al [18] has considered both local and global characteristics of a motion vector where curl and divergence of trajectories are used to define the collective motion patterns. This approach was useful in classifying the crowd behavior.

Kaelon Lloyd [19] et.al has proposed a real-time descriptors which have the ability to model the crowd dynamics by using a feature of grey-level occurrences. This method is computationally cheap and can provide a real-time description. Author has introduced measurement of inter frame equally which helps in the detection of violent behavior in a video scene.

Dheeraj Kumar [20] et.al has proposed an algorithm which is based on Visual Assessment of Tendency (VAT) based clustering algorithm for trajectory path analysis. A new clustering based framework is developed for anomaly detection. It is based on Minimum Spanning Tree that depends on efficient thresholding scheme. Based on the count of the path in the cluster, trajectories are classified. This method is applied for both vehicles and pedestrians.

In the field of intelligent video surveillance, automatic analysis of the video is challenging. Dan Xu [21] has proposed an algorithm Appearance and Motion Deep Net (AMDN). The algorithm uses a deep neural network for learning the feature representation. A double fusion pattern is also developed to determine both motion and appearance features separately to get the benefits of both traditional and late fusion. One-class SVM models are applied to predict the anomaly detection.

3. Proposed Model

This section describes the proposed framework to catch abnormality in a video scene. Figure 1 shows the complete flow of our proposed framework.

Figure 1. Proposed real-time framework for abnormal activity detection

The video consists of a number of frames f and a particular frame can be denoted by f_x , where x is the frame number. Frame f_x is considered to contain q number of sections obtained through simple gridding mechanism. Visual difference between frames is used to eliminate frame background [22]. Difference between frames f_x and f_{x-1} enables identification of grid sections where motion is observed.

Total energy observed for p^{th} motion vector entering section n at a^{th} frame i.e. f_a and exiting at f_b is computed using

$$\mathbb{E}_{n,p} = \int_0^{f_{a,p}-f_{b,p}} \mathbb{K} \cdot e^{-c_f f} df, \quad (1)$$

Where the decay coefficient is c_f and \mathbb{K} is a constant. Computation of $\mathbb{E}_{p,n}$ post integration is defined as

$$\mathbb{E}_{n,p} = (\mathbb{K} \times c_f^{-1})(1 - e^{-c_f(f_{a,p}-f_{b,p})}), \quad (2)$$

The total energy in section n considering a total p motion vectors at the f^{th} frame i.e. f_f is computed using

$$\mathbb{E}_n = \sum_{p=1}^p \frac{\mathbb{E}_{n,p}}{e^{c_f(f_{a,p}-f_{b,p})}} \quad (3)$$

If we diffuse these energy sources \mathbb{E}_n over entire frames of a video, it generates a Heatmap, which is defined as H_p at section n :

$$H_p = \frac{\sum_{m=1}^G \mathbb{E}_m \cdot e^{-c_s d(p,m)}}{G} \quad (4)$$

Where, E_m the energy of section is m , G is the total number of grid sections. c_s is the spatial coefficient and $d(p, m)$ denotes the distance between grid section p and m .

Once heat map is established, we try to find out the point of interests. In our system model, Harris corner detector is implemented for this purpose, which depends on auto correlation of a signal. It is a prevalent method which is invariant with respect to direction, scaling and noise.

Let us suppose an image source S containing a point (g, h) in the spatial domain. After a certain time duration point (g, h) changes its position by $(\Delta g, \Delta h)$, then the auto-correlation function $r(g, h)$ can be defined as:

$$r(g, h) = \sum_{\omega} [S(g_i, h_i) - S(g_i + \Delta g, h_i + \Delta h)]^2 \quad (5)$$

Where $S(\dots)$ represents image function and (g_i, h_i) denotes points on a window w . Shifted image can be expressed by a Taylor expansion:

$$\begin{aligned} S(g_i + \Delta g, h_i + \Delta h) \\ \approx S(g_i, h_i) \\ + [S_g(g_i, h_i), S_h(g_i, h_i)] \begin{bmatrix} \Delta g \\ \Delta h \end{bmatrix} \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

Here, $S_g(\dots)$ and $S_h(\dots)$ is the partial derivatives of g and h respectively. From equation 5 and 6:

$$r(g, h) = \sum_{\omega} \left([S_g(g_i, h_i), S_h(g_i, h_i)] \begin{bmatrix} \Delta g \\ \Delta h \end{bmatrix} \right)^2 \quad (7)$$

Computation of auto-correlation function $r(g, h)$ post summation is defined is:

$$r(g, h) = [\Delta g, \Delta h] M_S(g, h) \begin{bmatrix} \Delta g \\ \Delta h \end{bmatrix} \quad (8)$$

Where $M_S(g, h)$ is defined as:

$$\begin{aligned} M_S(g, h) \\ = \begin{pmatrix} \sum_{\omega} (S_g(g_i, h_i))^2 & \sum_{\omega} S_g(g_i, h_i) S_h(g_i, h_i) \\ \sum_{\omega} S_g(g_i, h_i) S_h(g_i, h_i) & \sum_{\omega} (S_h(g_i, h_i))^2 \end{pmatrix} \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

The symmetric matrix M_S of 2×2 gives the intensity values of neighborhood pixel. Let us assume that the Eigen value of M_S is λ_1 and λ_2 . Points of interest's region are depending on this λ value. If the value of λ_1 and λ_2 are very small, it means the local correlation function is flat in nature and hence no point of interest is found. If one value of λ is small and other is low, it means the auto correlation function is rigid which denotes an edge is found. If both the values of λ are high, it means the auto correlation function is peak shaped.

Once we get the point of interest for initial frame, we start finding out those points over next frame, it is called POI fitting, we implemented Lucas-Kanade algorithm [23] for this purpose. After POI fitting between frames, we get a set of vector

$$Z = \{Z_1, \dots, Z_N\} \{Z_i = (X_i, Y_i, D_i, \alpha_i)\} \quad (10)$$

Where X_i, Y_i denotes X and Y coordinate of individual feature i . D_i denotes the distance between the matched feature of two consecutive frames and α_i denotes the direction of motion of feature i .

If $E(X_i, Y_i)$ and $F(X_i, Y_i)$ are two matched feature point of two consecutive frames than Euclidian distance is defined as:

$$D_i = \sqrt{(FX_i - EX_i)^2 + (FY_i - EY_i)^2} \quad (11)$$

Using trigonometric function, we can also find the value of α_i :

$$\alpha_i = \arctan \left(\frac{Y_i}{X_i} \right) \quad (12)$$

Where $x_i = FX_i - EX_i, y_i = FY_i - EY_i$

The motion direction α_i for the i feature is calculated, but there are some potential problems, which will occur during the calculation of desire motion direction through equation 12, such as exceptions generation, out of phase, etc. To overcome this kind of problem we will apply $\arctanB(x_i, y_i)$ function that consider x_i and y_i as an argument values. Therefore, the precise motion direction α_i for the i feature is calculated by

$$\alpha_i = \arctanB(y_i, x_i) = \begin{cases} \emptyset \cdot \text{sign}(y_i) & \\ 0 & \\ \pi/2 \cdot \text{sign}(y_i) & \\ \text{undefined} & \\ (\pi - \emptyset) \cdot \text{sign}(y_i) & \\ \pi & \end{cases} \quad (13)$$

Equation (13) can be explained as follows:

If the $x_i > 0, y_i \neq 0$, then

$$\alpha_i = \emptyset \cdot \text{sign}(y_i)$$

If the $x_i > 0, y_i = 0$, motion direction α_i becomes zero. If the $x_i = 0, y_i \neq 0$, then

$$\alpha_i = \pi/2 \cdot \text{sign}(y_i)$$

The value $x_i = 0, y_i = 0$, then the motion detection become undefined. If $x_i < 0, y_i \neq 0$, then

$$\alpha_i = (\pi - \emptyset) \cdot \text{sign}(y_i)$$

Moreover, if $x_i < 0, y_i = 0$, then the precise motion direction α_i for the i feature is π . The function of sign (i.e. $\text{sign}(y_i)$) can be given by -1 if $y_i < 0$, 0 if $y_i = 0$ and 1 if $y_i > 0$. Therefore, the function $\arctanB(x, y)$ nicely handle the correct quadrant angle and the infinity slopes.

1.1 Fitting parameters of optical flow vector

a) Movement area ratio

In motion the area ratio involves each of the video frame, where the movement area ratio Ψ_R calculate the ratio of blocks number that containing motion and the total defined blocks number. Here, M and N has considered as the number of row and columns, which is used to estimate Ψ_R , where we divide individual video frame by $M \times N$ blocks. If some movements occur in one-block, then it can be said as one moving block. As we calculate, our total moving blocks (MBs) number to define Ψ_R such as:

$$\Psi_R = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{j=1}^M MB(i, j)}{M \times N} \quad (14)$$

b) Orientation variance ratio:

Here, we are estimating the variance of direction β_v by calculating the mean direction $\hat{\beta}$.

$$\beta_v = \frac{1}{n-1} \sum_{i=1}^n (\beta_i - \hat{\beta})^2 = \frac{1}{n-1} \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_i^2 - \frac{n}{n-1} \beta^{-2} \quad (15)$$

The ratio of variance to mean can be given by;

$$\beta_R = \frac{\beta_v}{\beta} \tag{16}$$

After optical flow vector fitting, we start segmenting the motion area based on created Heat-map. For this purpose, the watershed algorithm [24] is implemented in our experiment. This algorithm is fast and flexible for computing watershed area. Based on segmenting area we extract the feature vector which is utilized by BoF classifier [25] for classifying abnormal activity.

1.2 Bag of Features

After getting feature vectors, a visual vocabulary is developed. For this purpose we have used K-means clustering algorithm. By using this visual vocabulary, we quantize our feature vectors and the undertaken frame is represented by visual words. We train our machines to understand the frames better. For this purpose we have used the k-nearest neighbor classification method, which comes under discriminative methods of classification where all input vectors are assigned into two classes. Test data points are assigned by nearest training data points. For a new point, we find out a k-closest point from training data. In order to classify a model is created based on the Labels of the k-points.

Similarity measurement between histogram of two bag-of-words is defined by two distance functions, which are as follows:

$$D(h_1, h_2) = \sum_{i=1}^N |h_1(i) - h_2(i)| \tag{17}$$

$$D(h_1, h_2) = \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{(h_1(i) - h_2(i))^2}{h_1(i) + h_2(i)} \tag{18}$$

Where $D(h_1, h_2)$ denotes the distance between two different histograms, N denotes total number of bag-of-words, $h_1(i)$ & $h_2(i)$ are two different histograms of two bag-of-words.

4 Results and Discussions

This section 4 describes the outcome evaluation and performance of the proposed model. The model is designed in MATLAB user interface. The dataset that is considered for our proposed model is from the UMN. The dataset is converted into a number of frames, which are subjected to our proposed model. Extracted frames having both normal and abnormal activities, which needs to catch by proposed system. Figure 2-9 represents a frame having both normal and abnormal activities caught by the proposed system.

Figure 2: Crowd scenario

Figure 3: Abnormal Crowd scenario

Figure 4: Corridor scenario

Figure 5: AbnormalCorridor scenario

Figure 6: Court-yard scenario

Figure 7: Abnormal Court-yard scenario

Figure 8: Hit run scenario

Figure 9: Abnormal hit run scenario

In order to compare the system efficiency, ground truth is taken as a reference. The UMN dataset that is used for the study contains 4 types of circumstances: crowd, corridor, courtyard and hit and run. The number of frames extracted from these scenarios is 40, 34, 42 and 30 correspondingly. An individual frame level representation is shown in Figure 10-13 for each scenario.

Figure 10: Frame level comparison of proposed algorithm for crowd

Figure 11: Frame level comparison of proposed algorithm for corridor(scenario 2)

Figure 12: Frame level comparison of proposed algorithm for dataset courtyard (scenario 3)

Figure 13: Frame level comparison of proposed algorithm for dataset hit and run (scenario 4)

ROC Analysis

Receiver Operating Characteristics (ROC) is the most convenient way to show the performance of a binary classifier in graphical form. It is plotted between true positive rate and false positive rate at various threshold levels. Since applied binary BoF classifier, so ROC analysis is a better way to demonstrate its performance.

Figure 14-17 demonstrates ROC curve of different scenarios of UMN dataset first and second graph represents crowd and corridor

scenario respectively whereas the third and fourth graph represents courtyard and hit-run scenario.

Figure 14: ROC curve for scenario 1(crowd)

Figure 15: ROC curve for scenario 2(corridor)

Figure 16: ROC curve for scenario 3(courtyard)

Figure 17: ROC curve for scenario 4(Hit-run)

We have compared ROC results with another state of the art methods. ROC provides area under curve (AUC) which should be close to 1. High value of AUC means more accuracy. AUC value of different algorithm is shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Different method with AUC

Method	AUC (%)
SFM [26]	94.65
Sparse recons. [28]	99.62
Chaotic invariants [27]	99.45
Local statistics [29]	99.53
HMDT [30]	99.58
HOGHOS [31]	97.12
LMVD [32]	98.65
PROPOSED	99.6

5 Conclusion:

This paper described the analysis of crowd behavior using optical flow model along with BoF classification model. The proposed model is tested with UMN dataset. The motion area is identified by heat map which provides theregion of interest. Based on the heat map optical flow vector is extracted, which helps in getting feature vector. In theresultsection ROC analysis is performed. A frame level comparison is also demonstrated with ground truth. This proposed approach is well suited for real-time scenarios. Optical flow features are used to gather the feature vectors in the BoF classification model. This helps in building a classification model, which has an accuracy of 99.6 %.

References:

- [1] H. Liu, S. Chen and N. Kubota, "Intelligent Video Systems and Analytics: A Survey," in IEEE Transactions on Industrial Informatics, vol. 9, no. 3, pp. 1222-1233, Aug. 2013. doi: 10.1109/TII.2013.2255616
- [2] Salah, A.A.; Gevers, T.; Sebe, N.; Vinciarelli, A. Challenges of Human Behavior Understanding. Proceedings of the First International Conference on Human Behavior Understanding (HBU), Istanbul, Turkey, 22 August 2010; Springer-Verlag: Berlin, Germany, 2010; pp. 1–12.
- [3] W. Liu, R. W. H. Lau, X. Wang and D. Manocha, "Exemplar-AMMs: Recognizing Crowd Movements From Pedestrian Trajectories," in IEEE Transactions on Multimedia, vol. 18, no. 12, pp. 2398-2406, Dec. 2016. doi: 10.1109/TMM.2016.2598091
- [4] A. Bera, S. Kim and D. Manocha, "Realtime Anomaly Detection Using Trajectory-Level Crowd Behavior Learning," 2016 IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition Workshops (CVPRW), Las Vegas, NV, 2016, pp. 1289-1296. doi: 10.1109/CVPRW.2016.163
- [5] C. Chen, Y. Shao and X. Bi, "Detection of Anomalous Crowd Behavior Based on the Acceleration Feature," in IEEE Sensors Journal, vol. 15, no. 12, pp. 7252-7261, Dec. 2015. doi: 10.1109/JSEN.2015.2472960
- [6] O. P. Popoola and K. Wang, "Video-based abnormal human behavior recognition—A review," IEEE Trans. Syst., Man, Cybern. C, Appl. Rev., vol. 42, no. 6, pp. 865–878, Nov. 2012.
- [7] F. Santoro S. Pedro Z.H. Tan and T.B. Moeslund: "Crowd Analysis by Using Optical Flow and Density Based Clustering" 18th European Signal Processing Conference (EUSIPCO) Denmark August 2010.
- [8] A. Basharat A. Gritai and M. Shah. Learning Object Motion Patterns for Anomaly Detection and Improved Object Detection. In CVPR 2008.
- [9] Davis J (1999) Recognizing movement using motion histograms. In: MIT Media Lab Technical Report #487, March
- [10] Blei, David M. Andrew Y. Ng, and Michael I. Jordan (2003), "Latent Dirichlet Allocation," Journal of Machine Learning Research, 3, 993–1022.
- [11] Andrade, Ernesto L. et al. "Hidden Markov Models for Optical Flow Analysis in Crowds." I CPR (2006).
- [12] Y. Zhou, S. Yan, and T. S. Huang, "Detecting anomaly in videos from trajectory similarity analysis," in Proc. IEEE Int. Conf. Multimedia Expo., 2007, pp. 1087–1090.
- [13] V. Mahadevan, W. Li, V. Bhalodia and N. Vasconcelos, "Anomaly detection in crowded scenes," 2010 IEEE Computer Society Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition, San Francisco, CA, 2010, pp. 1975-1981. doi: 10.1109/CVPR.2010.5539872
- [14] Si Wu, Hau-San Wong, and Zhiwen Yu, "A Bayesian Model for Crowd Escape Behavior Detection," IEEE Trans. Circuits and Systems for Video Technology, vol. 24, no. 1, Jan. 2014. pp: 85-98
- [15] Robert Bensch, Nico Scherf, Jan Huiskens, Thomas Brox, and Olaf Ronneberger. 2017. Spatiotemporal Deformable Prototypes for Motion Anomaly Detection. Int. J. Comput. Vision 122, 3 (May 2017), 502-523. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11263-016-0934-1>
- [16] Yaping Yu, Wei Shen, He Huang, Zhijiang Zhang, "Abnormal event detection in crowded scenes using two sparse dictionaries with saliency," Journal of Electronic Imaging 26(3), 033013 (22 May 2017).
- [17] Xue, Y., Liu, P., Tao, Y., et al. (2017). Abnormal Prediction of Dense Crowd Videos by a Purpose-Driven Lattice Boltzmann Model. International Journal of Applied Mathematics and Computer Science, 27(1), pp. 181-194. Retrieved 17 Aug. 2017, from doi:10.1515/amcs-2017-0013
- [18] Shuang Wu, Hua Yang, Shibao Zheng, Hang Su, Yawen Fan, and Ming-Hsuan Yang, "Crowd behavior analysis via curl and divergence of motion trajectories," Internation Journal of Computer Vision, 2015, Under review, supplied in the supplementary materials.
- [19] Lloyd, Kaelon & Marshall, David & Moore, Simon & Rosin, Paul. (2016). Detecting Violent Crowds using Temporal Analysis of GLCM Texture. .
- [20] D. Kumar J. C. Bezdek S. Rajasegarar C. Leckie M. Palaniswami "A visual-numeric approach to clustering and anomaly detection for trajectory data" The Visual Computer pp. 1-17 2015.
- [21] Dan Xu, Yan Yan, Elisa Ricci, Nicu Sebe, Detecting anomalous events in videos by learning deep representations of appearance and motion, Computer Vision and Image Understanding, Volume 156, 2017, Pages 117-127, ISSN 1077-3142, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.cviu.2016.10.010>.
- [22] L. Li W. M. Huang I. Y. H. Gu Q. Tian "Foreground object detection in changing background based on color co-occurrence statistics" Proc. IEEE Workshop Applications of Computer Vision pp. 269-274 2002-Dec.
- [23] Dhara Patel and Saurabh Upadhyay. Article: Optical Flow Measurement using Lucas Kanade Method. International Journal of Computer Applications 61(10):6-10, January 2013.
- [24] L. Vincent and P. Soille, "Watersheds in digital spaces: an efficient algorithm based on immersion simulations," in IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence, vol. 13, no. 6, pp. 583-598, Jun 1991. doi: 10.1109/34.87344
- [25] S. O'Hara and B. A. Draper, "Introduction to the bag of features paradigm for image classification and retrieval," Computing Research Repository, vol. arXiv:1101.3354v1, 2011.
- [26] R. Mehran, A. Oyama, and M. Shah, "Abnormal crowd behavior detection using social force model," in IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition, CVPR, 2009, pp. 935–942.
- [27] S. Wu, B. E. Moore, and M. Shah, "Chaotic invariants of lagrangian particle trajectories for anomaly detection in crowded scenes," in IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition, CVPR, 2010, pp. 2054–2060.
- [28] Y. Cong, J. Yuan, and J. Liu, "Sparse reconstruction cost for abnormal event detection." in Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition, CVPR, 2011, pp. 3449–3456.
- [29] V. Saligrama and Z. Chen, "Video anomaly detection based on local statistical aggregates," in IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition, CVPR, 2012, pp. 2112–2119.
- [30] W. Li, V. Mahadevan, and N. Vasconcelos, "Anomaly detection and localization in crowded scenes," IEEE Trans. Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence, vol. 36, no. 1, pp. 18–32, 2014.
- [31] Rajashekhar B S, et. al, "Image augmentation using switching medial filter" published in Google scholar indexed UGC approved Journal, May2019
- [32] Rajashekhar B S and Manjunath N L " Novel switching median filter for image enhancement " Recent Trends in Signal Processing, Image Processing and VLSI, ICrtSIV DOI: 03.AETS.2014.5.324 © Association of Computer Electronics and Electrical Engineers (ACEEE), 2014.